

Optical and Electro-optical Materials Prepared by the Sol-Gel Method

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Although there are excellent contributions in the scientific literature covering most aspects of sol-gel hybrid materials for optics and electro-optics, this short review shall concentrate on the research activities of the Sol-Gel Group (SGG) at Madrid in this field, describing recent progress and interdisciplinary approaches to materials with novel properties.

I. Introduction

Hybrid materials for optics and electro-optics have been of interest to the sol-gel community since the first contributions in that field. However, the development of hybrid sol-gel coatings over recent years has turned out to be the most-demanded by the industrial sector, due to their capability of inducing new properties in a wide variety of materials.^[1] The possibility of incorporating organic dopants into transparent matrices allows the preparation of many different hybrid materials that find application in the field of optics and electro-optics.^[2] Excellent reviews summarizing the main activities in this field have been published by Sanchez et al.^[3,4] and Innocenzi and Lebeau.^[5] These new materials have been mainly applied as thin-film coatings, in whose porosity dopant molecules are allocated or attached to the hybrid network.^[6,7] These matrices can be tailor-made to design both the properties of the matrix itself and the properties of the pore cage, in terms of pore size and chemical environment, which will

have an important effect on the performance of the devices.^[8]

Over the last 20 years, hybrid materials for optics and photonics have reached a quite-mature situation, with some products already available on the market. However, the many difficulties relating to the replacement of existing technologies make it difficult to fully accomplish some of the new proposed challenges and developments. There is still much work to do in terms of multidisciplinary research in the areas of chemistry and physics to exploit the technical opportunity of creating optical and photonic materials that satisfy the requirements of a variety of applications and devices; important contributions are expected in the coming years from research on novel, hybrid, functional sol-gel materials.

This review describes the most-representative contributions of the SGG in the field of hybrid materials for optics and electro-optics. Hybrid coatings with potential applications as smart windows, radiation-protection coatings, coatings for optical lenses and photochromic materials can be found among the actual research lines of the SGG. Efforts are dedicated to the preparation of new materials via the sol-gel method, the characterization of their physicochemical properties and the study of the molecular interactions of the dopants with the embedding surfaces of the hybrid matrices. The light-matter interactions and optical properties of the resulting materials are evaluated as potential photonic devices.

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2. Gel-Glass-Dispersed Liquid-Crystal (GDLC) Materials

GDLCs consist of a dispersion of liquid-crystal (LC) microdroplets in a transparent, solid, thin-film matrix. Owing to their intrinsic properties, the birefringent LC molecules in each droplet adopt a director configuration (long-range preferred orientation) induced by the specific anchoring sites on the surfaces of the pores. Therefore, an opaque material is obtained due to the light scattering produced by the LC microdroplets (OFF state). If an electrical field that overcomes these anchoring forces is applied to such a material (ON-state), a reorientation of the LC molecules inside the microdroplets to the direction of the applied field takes place. In this situation, and provided that the matrix has a refractive index similar than that of the n_o of the liquid crystal, the material becomes transparent to the

Figure 1. Electro-optical window based on liquid-crystal dispersions in sol-gel matrices in the OFF (left) and ON (right) states.

incident light. Upon cessation of the application of the electric field, the molecules in the microdroplets recover their original preferred orientation and the films become opaque again. These materials are of an increasing interest for application as electronic liquid-crystal displays (LCDs), optical switches or light modulators. Among other advantages, GDLCs need no polarizers for operation and no surface treatment is required to scatter light in the OFF state. Pictures of a device in the OFF and ON states are shown in **Figure 1**.

Since the first work published on GDLCs,^[9,10] effort has been oriented to improving the performance of prototype devices using different modified silica matrices for the entrapment of LC microdroplets. Owing to its high versatility, the sol-gel method offers important advantages for the preparation of this kind of material, as there is a large choice of metal alkoxide precursors that allows the preparation of matrices with different physical and chemical properties.^[11] There are important parameters that must be taken into consideration for a successful preparation of GDLC films: the sols used for thin-film deposition must be clear and viscosity-stable to allow the preparation of homogeneous films and guarantee the reproducibility of the thin-film formation and properties. Moreover, phase separation between the LC and the matrix is one of the most-important steps in the preparation of GDLCs, and must occur simultaneously with the gelling and solidification of the matrix to allow the formation and stabilization of the LC droplets in the solid matrix.

The importance of the sol-gel process is evidenced by the possibility of controlling relevant parameters of the sol-gel reaction, such as the reactivity of the sol, as well as important properties of the resulting materials, such as the index of refraction, the thickness and the density of the matrix, which are decisive for the optimal performance of GDLC devices.

The preparation of GDLC materials in hybrid organic-inorganic matrices has opened the possibility of functionalizing the inner porosity of the gel-glass matrix where the LC droplets are located with different organic groups. This, in turn, allows the size of the pores and the polarity of their surface, and hence the anchoring forces of the pore surface, to be controlled, which determines the electro-optical properties of the resulting devices. The nature of the non-hydrolyzable organic functional group on the modified alkoxide precursors plays an important role in the formation of the LC droplets. It is known that during glass formation, these organic groups are oriented towards the pore cavities where the LC molecules will be allocated. Therefore, the size of the organic substituents and their affinity to the LC molecules will affect the size of the pores and the LC loading admitted by a specific matrix.

The dynamic properties of electro-optical devices are also strongly influenced by the nature of the organic functional groups used for the preparation of the thin films. The introduction of nonpolar groups results in a reduction of the anchoring forces of the matrix, as they hinder the electrostatic forces between the LC droplets and the OH groups on the silica surface. The effect is then more remarked when larger organic groups are incorporated at the pore surface. This reduction in the anchoring forces results in a reduction of the voltage required for the operation of the device and in faster transitions from the OFF to the ON state, when a given external field is applied (seconds to milliseconds). The recovery of the initial opacity (from the ON to the OFF state), when the LC molecules must reorient to their initial orientation based on the anchoring forces of the matrix surface, is particularly slower in functionalized matrices (several seconds) as compared with unmodified silica matrix (milliseconds). The use of hybrid matrices to prepare GDLC films also results in a marked narrowing of the droplet-size distribution and a weakening of the opacity of the samples in the OFF state. The stability of devices upon prolonged operation has been tested by switching the samples more than 1000 times between the ON and OFF states without any loss in their electro-optical properties.

With the aim of elucidating the interactions between the LC molecules in the droplet with the surface of the host matrix, we recently studied the molecular configurations adopted by the LCs inside the droplets and their dependence on the chemical composition of the matrix surface and the temperature.^[12] These configurations can be determined using polarized optical microscopy (POM) and a full-wave-sensitive tint plate (λ -plate) that produces different colorations in the microscope image depending on the orientation of the LC molecules. Two different molecular configurations were observed, namely radial and bipolar, in which the LC molecules were aligned perpendicular or parallel to the confining surface, respectively. The radial configuration was observed in a sample with large amounts of functional alkyl groups in the matrix and at low temperatures (close to the crystallization of the LC), while the bipolar configuration was observed at higher temperatures and for lower organic loadings. The results show the importance of this surface in terms of both the shape of the functional groups and their polar character in the determination of the preferred orientation of LC molecules on the surface (**Figure 2**).

3. Electro-optical Devices Based on Biofilm Structures

Very recently, in co-operation with the National Centre of Biotechnology (CSIC),^[13] we developed a new electro-optical device based in the same principles of GDLCs, in which the host matrix for the liquid crystal (LC) was made by bacterial activity (a biofilm).^[14] In order to exhibit the electro-optical effect, liquid-crystal dispersion devices require a specific structure in terms of the macroporosity and refractive index of the matrix. Efficient light scattering (in the OFF state) is only obtained when the LC forms microdomains in the porosity of the embedding matrix; moreover, the index of refraction of the matrix must be similar to that of the ordinary index of the LC molecules

Figure 2. Schematic representation of pore surfaces showing different surface-anchoring properties of LC molecules (5CB): a) Radial anchoring. b) Bipolar anchoring.

to attain transparency fully in the ON state, when the LC molecules are aligned with the electrical field. The specific tridimensional architecture and the optical properties of a biofilm created by the bacterium *Pseudomonas putida* mt-2 complies with these requirements and was therefore used to build-up the electro-optical device (Figure 3). The biofilm was deposited on transparent conductive glass (indium tin oxide (ITO)) in order

to allow the application of an external electrical field. The LC molecules were embedded in the biofilm matrix by capillary filling, followed by thermal treatment with hot air to ensure the complete wetting of the biofilm matrix with the LC material. The electro-optical device showed an opaque state with a light transmittance of about 6%. The application of low effective voltages (<10 V) resulted in a fast transition into a very-clear transparent state ($T > 75\%$) in the range of milliseconds.

These pioneering results^[15] account for the first use of bacteria-created biofilms for the preparation of optical devices, and open a new tendency in multidisciplinary research towards exploiting natural structures as potential hosts for advanced devices.

4. Photochromic Organic-Inorganic Hybrid Materials

Photochromism is the reversible transformation of a chemical species between two forms that have different absorption spectra, induced by the absorption of electromagnetic radiation.^[16] Naphthopyran compounds are one of the most-studied photochromic compounds, due to the possibility of obtaining a photochromic response over a wide range of the visible spectrum from yellow to red. Analogously to spiro-oxazines, these molecules undergo a strong change in coloration when irradiated with UV light, due to the reversible heterolytic scission of the $C(sp^3)-O$ bond of the pyranic ring, leading to the formation of colored merocyanine structures. The system may revert to the initial state both thermally (in the dark) or photochemically (in visible light).

We recently demonstrated the feasibility of introducing photochromic naphthopyran derivatives into sol-gel organically modified silica (ormosil) matrices, and the effects of different organic functional substituents in the ormosil matrix on the photochromic properties of the embedded molecules.^[17] Different photochromic naphthopyran derivatives have been incorporated in sol-gel-prepared hybrid matrices to characterize their photochromic properties. The use of inorganic or hybrid matrices for the incorporation of the photochromic molecules leads to materials with a higher photostability, as compared with polymeric matrices that are limited by their own low stability upon irradiation with UV light.

The resulting coatings are transparent and colorless and show a rapid and deep coloration upon exposure to UV light (365 nm), acquiring blue, yellow, red and green colors, see Figure 4 (the green color was obtained by the mixture of yellow and blue photochromic dyes).

The most-marked properties of photochromic naphthopyran molecules embedded in sol-gel-prepared thin films can be controlled by the composition of the host hybrid matrix. Functionalization of the matrix allows the incorporation of a large amount of dye molecules in its porosity, which is of a great importance from the point of view of applications, as it allows films that develop a deep coloration upon irradiation with UV light to be obtained. In addition, the nature and amount of the organic functional groups incorporated in the matrix have an important effect on the size and shape of the pores and the chemical composition of the surface, which determines the polarity of

Figure 3. Liquid-crystal dispersions in biofilms created by bacterial activity: a) FE-SEM image of the biofilm. b) Detail of the macroporous structure. c,d) The electro-optical device in the OFF and ON states.

the pore cage where the photochromic molecules are located. Therefore, the functionalization of the matrix can be used to control important properties of the photochromic molecules, such as their absorption spectra and their bleaching kinetics, which are greatly affected by the polarity of the environment.

In a recent study, we demonstrated the possibility of drastically reducing the photodegradation of photochromic molecules upon prolonged exposure to UV light by the functionalization of the host matrix.^[18] The loss of photochromic properties, commonly referred to as fatigue, limits the use of

Figure 4. Picture of the thin films prepared with different photochromic dyes, before and after irradiation with UV light.

photochromic molecules in outdoor applications or in environments with strong UV radiation. The photostability of photochromic molecules embedded in an ormosil matrix upon prolonged exposure to UV light was found to depend strongly on the composition of the embedding matrix. The introduction of organic functional groups to the inner pore surface of the matrix affects the stability of the molecules in terms of the effectiveness of the interaction between the photochromic molecules and the surface of the pores, and can thus be used as an important tool to increase the photostability of a photochromic dye in a device. The incorporation of phenyl groups into hybrid silica matrices results in a reduction of the photodegradation of the dye molecules by a factor of 9, as compared with that in unmodified silica matrices.^[18]

Photochromic hybrid materials have attracted considerable attention owing to their potential applications as photochromic decorations, variable-optical-transmission materials, UV sensors, waveguide/fiber-optic optical-delay generators, optical memory devices, holographic recording media, or non-linear optics.^[17] Recently, we reported

on a novel photochromic hybrid coating that had a remarkable long-term stability for both the colored state and the colorless state in the dark (bistability).^[19] The coatings consisted of a dispersion of a commercial spiro-oxazine in a functionalized sol-gel hybrid matrix that acquired a deep purple coloration upon irradiation with UV light. The reversible coloration/bleaching process could only be achieved by irradiating the coatings with UV and visible light, respectively. This reversibility of the recording/erasing process of the photochromic coatings makes their use as optical data-recording media possible.

The ability to control the photochromic properties and the photostability of naphthopyran and spiro-oxazine molecules by varying the chemical composition of the embedding matrix and the sol-gel preparation and processing parameters is an important tool with great interest for the design of materials with defined properties.

5. Random Lasers in Dye-Doped Nanostructured Silica Gels

Since first proposed by Letokhov in 1967, lasing in random media has become the subject of intense theoretical and experimental studies due to the important scientific and technological implications of this new research field.^[20] Within the class of dye random lasers, laser dyes are used to provide the optical-gain amplification, whereas the scattering typically comes from a suspension of particles in a dye solution. However, a different approach was followed by our group to achieve random lasing. Rhodamine 6G (Rh6G) dye was embedded in solid, porous silica nanoparticles that could be either incorporated into a bulk-silica-gel matrix or directly dispersed within

undoped silica nanoparticles. The advantages of such a material are its solid-state nature, quenched disorder, high laser-like emission efficiency, and the possibility of being functionalized for various applications in the field of biosensors or biotracers. In a recent study,^[21] the authors demonstrated random-laser action in a grown powder made of a silica gel containing 2 wt% Rh6G-SiO₂ nanoparticles and in a dispersed powder sample containing the same amount of fluorescent nanoparticles. Moreover, we demonstrated that their random-laser-emission dynamics can be accurately described by using a light-diffusive propagation model with the feedback provided by the powder.

On the other hand, multiphoton-pumped frequency-upconversion lasing in dye-doped liquid and polymer systems has been one of the most interesting topics in non-linear optics and quantum electronics in recent years.^[22] The pursued main goal has been to attain ultrashort-wavelength lasing, which is useful for data storage, frequency-upconversion imaging, and, no-less important, for a better understanding of the interactions between intense optical fields and multiphoton active materials.^[23] Despite extensive published reports on laser-like emission following single-photon excitation, just a few researchers have addressed the issue of multiphoton-induced random lasing. In recent work, the authors experimentally demonstrated for the first time two-photon-pumped random lasing in a ground powder of a silica gel containing 2 wt% Rh6G-doped silica nanoparticles.^[24] Compared with other dye random media, the advantages and applications of the studied system were the same as cited above for one-photon-pumped random lasing. At present, this field is being thoroughly investigated by the authors with the aim of improving the material efficiency.

6. UV-Protective Coatings

Damaging UV light, natural or artificial, is responsible for the decomposition and degradation of organic matter, such as the discoloration of dyes and pigments, the yellowing of plastics, and the loss of gloss and mechanical properties (cracking) (Figure 5). Manufacturers have a great interest in offering products that remain unaltered for long periods of time under the worst light-exposure conditions.

We have developed highly efficient UV-absorbing coatings by the sol-gel method based on the dispersion of UV-absorber (UVA) molecules in a hybrid ormosil sol-gel matrix in order to reduce the undesirable effects of UV light on materials. The UVA molecules used in these coatings are derivatives of benzophenone, which present a very-efficient mechanism of dissipation of energy (excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT)), making these molecules highly photostable under UV light. The resulting UV-protective coatings showed a high efficiency for the protection of organic materials, as shown in previous papers,^[25,26] where the photodegradation rates of a sensitive fluorescence-dye-doped film were 14 times slower when the UV-absorbing coating was applied. The matrix allowed the incorporation of large amounts of UVA molecules, resulting in coatings with very-strong absorption in the 275–400 nm range and having a thickness of only 1 μm. On the other hand,

Figure 5. UV-protective coatings for artwork.

the coatings were fully transparent in the visible region of the spectrum and did not affect the optical properties of the materials that needed to be protected. Moreover, the highly efficient UV-absorbing coatings can be applied and cured at room temperature, making the application of these coatings possible on a very-wide variety of materials, especially on heat-sensitive materials.

The development of materials or components that show a high photostability under UV radiation is mandatory in space missions, where the degradation of materials by UV light is even more pronounced than on the Earth's surface. Advanced optical devices used in satellites or ships very often include materials and compounds susceptible to degradation and, therefore, they need to be protected. In this sense, effort is also oriented to the development of UV-protective coatings that can withstand the strong UV radiation in the space environment.

7. A Sol-Gel-Based Magneto-optical Device for the NANOSAT Space Mission

The Spanish Space Agency, Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA),^[27] launched in 2004 the first nanosatellite, called NANOSAT-01 (Figure 6), on board an Ariane 5 European rocket from French Guyana. The satellite consists of

Figure 6. NANOSAT-01.

a hexagonal device less than 19 kg in weight and with a diameter of about 50 cm, which describes a low earth orbit (LEO) at an altitude of 655 km. The main objective of the satellite is to probe the operation and performance of micro and nanotechnologies in the space environment. One of the scientific experiments implemented on board was the sol-gel-based magnetic nanosensor.

The magnetic sol-gel nanosensor is responsible for the positioning and orientation of the satellite by the detection of the Earth's magnetic field. The sensor consists of a dispersion of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ magnetic nanoparticles in a transparent silica matrix prepared using the sol-gel procedure. This nanocomposite, exhibiting the magneto-optical Faraday effect, was implemented as the heart of the magnetic nanosensor.^[28] The complementary systems, such as the detection optics and the electronics required for the operation of the nanosensor, were developed according to the requirements and performance of the sol-gel nanosensor.^[29] The design of the nanosensor and the complementary systems also had to comply with the strong vibrations imposed by the launch procedures and the harsh space-environment conditions. The nanosensor was designed for a 3–6-year lifetime in orbit. Tests were carried out to check the performance of the nanosensor in-orbit, under the extreme environmental space conditions.

Based on the experience of multidisciplinary scientific and technological research groups on nanotechnology in Spain, a sol-gel-based magneto-optical sensor, designed and developed to

measure the magnetic parameters of the Earth, was integrated into NANOSAT-01 to fulfil the operational requirements of the satellite. From the results obtained from the nanosensor, we consider that, from the point of view of sol-gel technologies, the development of an advanced device from its chemical design in the laboratory to its implementation into a satellite, now in orbit, is a very-promising achievement, and encourages us to continue collaborating in future scientific space missions.

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